

(A) Functional principal component analysis using Fourier basis functions with no smoothing

(B) Functional principal component analysis using Fourier basis functions with common-optimal smoothing

(C) Functional principal component analysis using Fourier basis functions with individual-optimal smoothing

(D) Functional principal component analysis using B-spline basis functions with no smoothing

(E) Functional principal component analysis using B-spline basis functions with common-optimal smoothing

(F) Functional principal component analysis using B-spline basis functions with individual-optimal smoothing

*concentration values <LOQ replaced by a random draw from a uniform distribution on the interval [0, LOQ]